

Growth aspects of 4-Dimethylamino-*N*-methyl Stilbazolium Tosylate (DAST) organic single crystals

Dr. P. Kalaiselvi^a, Dr. S. Alfred Cecil Raj^{a*} and Dr. S. Joseph Selvaraj^b

^a Department of Physics, St. Joseph's college(Autonomous), Tiruchirapalli- 620 002, India.

^b Department of Chemistry, St. Joseph's college(Autonomous), Tiruchirapalli- 620 002, India.

Abstract

To obtain large SHG efficiencies, the organic ionic salt crystal 4-Dimethylamino-*N*-Methyl Stilbazolium Tosylate (DAST) was synthesized and characterized using proton NMR, powdered XRD and elemental analysis. Moreover, DAST seed crystals have grown from solution using a variety of solvents with three different way of synthesis. The solvents were chosen namely allyl alcohol, acetonitrile and methanol. Among these, methanol and acetonitrile are preferred as best solvents. Albeit lot of difficulties were faced to avoid or control the hydration because DAST has the tendency to form as DAST.H₂O and in which influence the symmetry also. DAST crystallizes as both centro-symmetric and non-centro-symmetric nature depends upon the solvent used. The grown crystals where appeared as dark green and orange-red colour and they were also subjected to FTIR, NMR, PXRD, SXRD for confirmation studies. From Powder XRD hydrated peak has acquired. Subsequently, repeated action has taken to rectify the hydrous form of DAST. Moreover correlation was found at hydrous peak acquired at NMR, FTIR and PXRD. During growth suitable oil is sprayed at the surface to reduce this hydration.